

1 **Why to breed disease-resilient livestock, and how**

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25 **Abstract**

26 Background: Combat and control of epidemic and endemic diseases form a considerable cost to
27 livestock production. Much research is dedicated to breeding disease resilient livestock, but this is
28 not yet a common objective in practical breeding programs. We investigate how future breeding
29 programs may benefit from recent research.

30 Main body: We define disease resilience in terms of its component traits resistance (R: the ability of
31 a host animal to limit within-host pathogen burden (PB)) and tolerance (T: the ability of an infected
32 host to limit the damage caused by a given PB), and model the host's production performance as a
33 reaction norm on PB, depending on R and T.

34 Based on this we derive equations for the economic values of resilience and its component traits. A
35 case study on PRRS in pigs illustrates that the economic value for increasing production in
36 infectious conditions through selection for R and T can be more than three times higher than by
37 selection for production in disease-free conditions. Whilst this reaction norm model of resilience is
38 helpful for quantifying the relationship to its component traits, its parameters are difficult and
39 expensive to quantify. We consider the consequences of ignoring R and T in breeding programs that
40 measure resilience as production in infectious conditions with unknown PB – particularly, the risk
41 that the genetic correlation between R and T (r_{GR-T}) is unfavourable (antagonistic) and that a
42 trade-off between them neutralizes the resilience improvement. We describe four approaches to
43 avoid such antagonisms: (1) produce sufficient PB records to estimate r_{GR-T} and check for
44 antagonisms – if found, continue routine PB recording and if not shift to cheaper proxies for PB; (2)
45 selection on QTL known to influence both R and T in favourable ways; (3) rapid modification
46 towards near-complete resistance or tolerance, (4) re-defining resilience as the animal's capacity to
47 resist (or recover from) the perturbation caused by an infection, measured as temporal deviations of
48 production traits in within-host longitudinal data series.

49 Conclusion: All four alternatives offer promising break-throughs in genetic improvement of disease
50 resilience; most rely on technological and methodological developments and innovation in
51 automated data generation.

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55 **Background**

56 Infectious diseases form a major limiting factor to the sustainability and profitability of livestock
57 production worldwide. Reduced production performance, fertility and survival makes infectious
58 disease the number one threat to carbon neutral farming, which has become a major goal in many
59 countries worldwide. Table 1 summarizes estimated costs of combating them on the national level,
60 where relevant compared to the value of estimated genetic trend in production and/or reproduction
61 traits around the reporting year. The first five entries represent cases where a major epidemic was
62 dealt with by population-wide culling; this leads to costs of the order of € 100 to € 200 per animal,
63 dwarfing any achievable earnings from genetic improvement (note that the cost of ASF combat in
64 China includes only the material loss and not the resulting 2.5-fold increase in the retail price of pig
65 meat). The next six entries represent the ongoing annual costs of endemic disease control (and of
66 one minor epidemic) and show that those costs range from 2.7 to 7.6 times the annual value of
67 genetic improvement (ΔG) for production and/or reproduction traits. Similar information can be
68 found in (1, Chapters 16-20).

69 **Table 1 to appear here.**

70 In line with the above, and considering climate change, antimicrobial resistance, and changes in
71 farming practices that heighten disease emergence, disease resilience has become one of the most

72 desirable attributes of livestock. Nevertheless, the livestock breeding sector to date practices little
73 explicit selection for traits related to disease resilience. Several pig and poultry breeding companies
74 select for reduced mortality rates (which also have very high economic values) based on data
75 recorded on close relatives of nucleus selection candidates, grown in commercial conditions.
76 Although this can lead to solid ΔG trends in survival and production (e.g. (2); his Figure 3), overall
77 mortality has many more causes than infectious disease – so the relationship to disease resilience is
78 unclear and variable, and it is difficult to extrapolate to newly emerging diseases. Other companies
79 aim to breed for increased host resistance to specific diseases (e.g. (3) in pigs) which usually
80 requires routine challenge tests (e.g. (4, 5) in salmon; (6) in poultry) or extensive recording of
81 resistance traits in natural challenge conditions (e.g. (7) in sheep; (8) in cattle; (9) in rabbits).

82 Recently disease tolerance has been proposed as an alternative breeding goal trait (10-12), but to
83 our knowledge no breeding company to date carries out explicit selection for increased tolerance of
84 animals to any type of infection.

85 The system of disease resilience, resistance and tolerance carries confusing terminology: the three
86 terms are often used interchangeably to describe the same trait (e.g. mortality), and the definition of
87 resilience and the approaches to measure it on individual animals are ambiguous. Explicit selection
88 for resistance and tolerance requires extensive routine data recording, and sometimes specific
89 challenge tests – this leads to considerable investment for breeding companies, and the associated
90 cost-benefit analysis requires sound estimates of the economic values of these traits.

91 This paper has three objectives. First, to develop a unified framework to define resilience in terms
92 of its component traits resistance and tolerance. Second, to derive the economic values of these
93 three traits, with an example for PRRS in pigs. Third, to discuss applications and the way forward
94 in breeding disease resilient livestock.

95 **Main text**

96 **2. Disease resilience and its component traits disease resistance and tolerance**

97 Disease **resilience** in the context of livestock production was first defined as the ability of a host
98 animal to maintain a reasonable level of productivity when challenged by infection (13). Disease
99 resilience is assessed by comparing production performance of an individual or a family (e.g. a
100 sire's daughter group) between environments with different pathogen burden (14); in more
101 quantitative terms, the reaction norm of performance on environmental pathogen burden, i.e. a
102 continuous trait (15). Disease resilience captures two complementary host defense mechanisms
103 against pathogens: resistance and tolerance (16).

104 Disease **resistance** is the ability of a host animal to limit its within-host pathogen burden, either by
105 preventing infection in the first place or by inhibiting within-host pathogen replication (17, 18). In
106 simple terms: how does the immune system respond to the environmental pathogen burden? As
107 such it determines to what extent the *environmental* pathogen burden leads to *within-host* pathogen
108 burden; it is therefore most accurately quantified by continuous measures of within-host pathogen
109 burden (e.g. viremia or bacterial / parasite counts).

110 Disease **tolerance** is the ability of an infected host to limit the damage caused by a given within-
111 host pathogen burden (17, 18) without necessarily reducing this pathogen burden as such (19). In
112 simple terms: how does the body cope with preventing or repairing the damage inflicted either by
113 the pathogen or by the activated immune system? In quantitative livestock terms: the change in host
114 performance as pathogen burden changes, i.e. the slope of the reaction norm of production
115 performance on *within-host* pathogen burden (20): a continuous trait again. Confusingly, the term

116 "tolerance" has often been used to refer to the resilience mechanism that is based on *environmental*
117 pathogen burden as described above (21-23).

118 **Robustness**, in the context of intensive livestock production, refers to the combination of a high
119 production potential with high resilience to external stressors (such as environmental pathogen
120 burden), allowing for unproblematic expression of that production potential in a wide variety of
121 environmental conditions (24, 25). Very similar to general resilience to a variety of stressors,
122 focusing in particular on high-performance genotypes.

123 **Figure 1 to appear here.**

124 Figure 1 a-c illustrates the quantitative relationship between the various resilience traits for two host
125 animals (red 1, blue 2) with different performance potential (P_0 , expressed at zero pathogen
126 burden), different resistance against the pathogen (R), and different tolerance to infection (T) with
127 environmental pathogen burden or challenge dose PB_E . For ease of quantification, PB_E is specified
128 here in within-host pathogen burden units corresponding to a hypothetical reference host with zero
129 resistance to the pathogen. Similar to P_0 and to the *actual* environmental pathogen burden in field
130 conditions, this reference value is usually unknown but is useful for quantifying the relative role of
131 the environmental pathogen burden for resilience, and the economic value of resilience traits (see
132 Section 3.1). Figure 1 shows resilience and tolerance, following (15) as the classical reaction norm
133 of change in performance (P) in relation to pathogen burden: $P = P_0 + \beta \times PB$ (where slope $\beta \leq 0$).

134 In order to keep this model easily traceable, we quantify tolerance here as $T = -1 / \beta$, so that $T \geq 0$,
135 and a value of 0 represents complete absence of tolerance. Likewise for resistance, $R \geq 0$ and a
136 value of 0 represents complete absence of resistance. For both traits a numeric increase represents
137 improvement for the host, and a negative correlation is unfavourable. Resistance is measured in
138 terms of pathogen burden units: different host resistance levels cause reduction of PB_E down to
139 different levels of the realized PB_w .

140 In Figure 1a, the performance potential $P_{0,2}$ of individual 2 (in blue) is higher than that of individual
141 1 (in red) $P_{0,1}$, but its realized performance $P_{PBE,2}$ in infectious conditions PBE is lower than $P_{PBE,1}$.
142 This is because individual 2 is less resistant to infection (lower reduction from PBE to PBW :
143 $R_2 < R_1$) and also less tolerant to it (steeper slope: β_2 is more strongly negative than β_1) than
144 individual 1. In Figure 1b, the tolerance levels are the same as in 1a, but the resistance levels are
145 reversed: now individual 2 (in blue) is more resistant than individual 1 ($R_2 > R_1$); this causes a
146 stronger reduction from PBE to PBW in individual 2, climbing a longer stretch of the (still steep)
147 reaction norm, and this reduces the difference in realized performance P_{PBE} between both
148 individuals. In Figure 1c, the tolerance and resistance levels are the same as in 1b, but the
149 environmental pathogen burden PBE is lower; hence individual 2's stronger resistance can now
150 reduce PBE to a more favourable PBW level, neutralizing its lower tolerance; with that its P_{PBE} is
151 now higher than that of individual 1.

152 Figure 1 a-c demonstrates how different levels of performance can be achieved, depending on the
153 environmental challenge, and on an individual's performance potential, resistance and tolerance,
154 and the correlations between these. These concepts are formulated into a mathematical model in
155 equation (1a), where each host's actual performance at a given PBE level (and at this host's
156 associated PBW level) is given as

$$157 \quad P_{PBE} = P_0 - \frac{1}{T} \times PBW = P_0 - \frac{1}{T} \times (PBE - R). \quad (1a)$$

158 Note that this can be rearranged as

$$159 \quad P_{PBE} = \left[P_0 + \frac{R}{T} \right] - \frac{1}{T} \times PBE \quad (1b)$$

160 ...i.e. a reaction norm on the environmental pathogen burden, in line with the classical definition of
161 resilience of above. According to equations (1a) and (1b), infectious challenge ($PBE \geq 0$) reduces
162 performance, and resilience to the pathogen constrains this reduction: less of a reduction for more

163 tolerant hosts (with larger T in equation (1a)) and for more resistant hosts (with larger R in equation
164 (1a)).

165

166 3. The economic value of disease resilience traits

167 3.1 Theory

168 Economic values of resistance, tolerance and resilience can be derived from the relationships of
169 Figure 1 and equation (1a), as follows.

170 The partial derivative of equation (1a) with respect to resistance is

$$171 \frac{\partial P_{PBE}}{\partial R} = \frac{1}{T} \quad (2a)$$

172 From that, the marginal economic value (MEV) of resistance is

$$173 MEV(R) = \frac{\partial P_{PBE}}{\partial R} \times MEV(P) = \frac{1}{T} \times MEV(P), \quad (2b)$$

174 where MEV(P) is the MEV of the production trait under consideration. Hence improvement of
175 resistance is worth more at lower tolerance levels (low T), and when production performance is
176 worth more.

177 Likewise, the partial derivative of equation (1a) with respect to tolerance is

$$178 \frac{\partial P_{PBE}}{\partial T} = \frac{PB_E - R}{T^2}, \quad (3a)$$

179 a function of the infectious level and of the population means of resistance and of tolerance itself.

180 From that, the MEV of tolerance is

$$181 MEV(T) = \frac{\partial P_{PBE}}{\partial T} \times MEV(P) = \frac{PB_E - R}{T^2} \times MEV(P) \quad (3b)$$

182 Hence an improvement of tolerance is worth more (i) if the infectious challenge is high (high PB_E),
183 (ii) at lower resistance levels (low R), (iii) at lower tolerance levels (low T), and (iv) when
184 production performance is worth more. When resistance is strong enough to eliminate the pathogen

185 completely (i.e. when $R \geq PB_E$), improvement of tolerance has a zero value. Likewise, the economic
 186 value of tolerance increases at a diminishing rate of return with increasing levels of tolerance.

187 The economic value of resilience is the value of the amount of performance recaptured by a unit
 188 improvement in resilience, along a reaction norm from P_{PBE} upwards towards P_0 . This will be due to
 189 improvements in resistance and/or tolerance, in any feasible combination. Figure 1d illustrates the
 190 principle. The starting position is based on initial resistance level R and initial tolerance level T ,
 191 with pathogen burden P_{BW1} and performance P_{PBW1} . From there, tolerance is increased by ΔT (from
 192 T to T') and resistance by ΔR , leading to a new position on a new reaction norm, with performance
 193 P_{PBW2} .

194 The increase in performance is ΔP :

$$195 \Delta P = P_{PBW2} - P_{PBW1} = \left[P_0 - \frac{PB_E - (R + \Delta R)}{T + \Delta T} \right] - \left[P_0 - \frac{PB_E - R}{T} \right] = \frac{PB_E - R}{T} - \frac{PB_E - (R + \Delta R)}{T + \Delta T} \quad (4a)$$

196 Recalling equations (2b) and (3b), deriving from them that $\frac{PB_E - R}{T} = \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)}$, and changing to
 197 differentials (from ΔP to dP), this can be rewritten as:

$$198 dP = \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)} - \frac{T}{T + dT} \times \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)} + \frac{dR}{T + dT} = \frac{dT}{T + dT} \times \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)} + \frac{dR}{T + dT} \quad (4b)$$

199 With dT small enough for $T + dT \approx T$, this simplifies to:

$$200 dP \approx \frac{dT}{T} \times \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)} + \frac{dR}{T} = dT \times \frac{MEV(R)}{MEV(P)} \times \frac{MEV(T)}{MEV(R)} + dR \times \frac{MEV(R)}{MEV(P)} = \frac{dT \times MEV(T) + dR \times MEV(R)}{MEV(P)} \quad (4c)$$

201 Note that for $dT = 0$, $\frac{dP}{dR} = \frac{1}{T}$ as in equation (2a); for $dR = 0$, $\frac{dP}{dT} = \frac{PB_E - R}{T^2}$ as in equation (3a).

202 The amount of recaptured performance of equation (4c) represents an economic value of
 203 $dP \times MEV(P) \approx dT \times MEV(T) + dR \times MEV(R)$ money units. Hence the MEV of disease resilience
 204 follows from the MEVs of its component traits resistance and tolerance, weighted by their specific

205 contributions to a change in the composite. As such it cannot be quantified without knowledge of
206 those contributions.

207 **3.2. Case study: the economic value of resilience of growing pigs to PRRS virus infections**

208 PRRS in pigs is widely considered as one of the most economically important viral disease in pigs
209 worldwide (26), yet the economic value of resilience to this disease is currently not known.
210 Estimates can be derived by applying the model of above to data from a large scale PRRS virus
211 challenge experiment where piglets were infected with the same dose of a virulent PRRS virus
212 strain at about 30 days of age (27). Lough et al. (28) derived tolerance estimates from individual
213 body weight and viremia records on 1011 of these young pigs by linear regression of performance
214 on pathogen burden. Here, performance is the average growth rate from 14 to 42 days post-
215 infection; pathogen burden is $AUC(\log VL)$, i.e. the area under the curve of log-transformed viremia
216 measurements, in that same period ((28), additional files #2). The average change in growth rate in
217 this population per unit increase of viremia and the standard deviation of the 1011 individual
218 regression coefficients are $\beta = -0.002660$ and $\sigma_P(\beta) = 0.00418$ kg/d per $AUC(\log VL)$, respectively.
219 From that, $T = 375.9$.

220 The genetic standard deviations (σ_G) of growth rate, of $AUC(\log VL)$, and of the reaction norm
221 slope in this data are 0.0549 kg/d, 9.22 $AUC(\log VL)$ units, and 0.0000924 kg/d per $AUC(\log VL)$
222 unit, respectively. From the σ_G of growth rate (i.e. of P_{PBE}), the σ_G of P_0 can be derived (see the
223 additional file for the derivation) as 0.011 kg/d.

224 The MEV of growth rate in pigs of this age range in Denmark was estimated by Ask (29) as DKK
225 110 = € 15 per kg/d. In the absence of trade-offs with resistance and tolerance, an **improvement of**
226 **the genetic potential for nursery-stage growth rate P_0 by one σ_G unit has then a value of 0.011**
227 **× 15 = € 0.165 per pig.**

228 When challenged with PRRS virus infection, and in the absence of trade-offs with performance
229 potential and tolerance, an improvement of PRRS resistance that would lead to a reduction of
230 AUC(logVL) by one σ_G (9.22 units) would increase nursery-stage growth rate (in this population
231 with its average tolerance level, and in this environment with its P_{BE}) by $9.22 \times 0.00266 = 0.0245$
232 kg/d. **Such an increase in resistance has a value of $0.0245 \times 15 = \text{€ } 0.37$ per pig.**

233 For the MEV of PRRS tolerance, consider a tolerance reaction norm that is one σ_G (i.e. 0.0000924
234 kg/d per AUC(logVL) unit) shallower (so that $\beta = -0.002568$, and from that $T = 389.5$) than the
235 current population average ($T = 375.9$). At zero pathogen burden, the two tolerance levels lead to
236 the same growth rate, and tolerance has a zero MEV; with increasing P_{BW} viremia levels (due to
237 decreasing resistance levels in the host) the contrast in growth rate increases and therefore the MEV
238 of tolerance increases. In other words, the MEV of tolerance depends on the resistance level in the
239 target population, as per equation (3b). At the highest viremia level in this data (i.e. 181.4
240 AUC(logVL) units, in this population with its average resistance level, and in this environment with
241 its P_{BE}) an **improvement of PRRS tolerance** by one genetic standard deviation would increase
242 nursery-stage growth rate by $0.0000924 \times 181.4 = 0.01676$ kg/d with **an economic value of € 0.25**
243 **per pig** (again in the absence of trade-offs with performance potential and resistance).

244 An **improvement of resilience** due to simultaneous improvement of resistance and tolerance (each
245 by one σ_G , i.e. $\Delta R = 9.22$ and $\Delta T = 13.6$) would then lead to a maximum (because calculated at the
246 highest viremia level in this data) performance recapture of $\Delta P = 0.0245 + 0.0168 = 0.041$ kg/d,
247 with **an economic value of EUR $0.37 + 0.25 = \text{€ } 0.62$ per pig**. As an indirect selection strategy for
248 performance at the highest viremia level in this data, it would deliver $0.62 / 0.165 = 3.7$ times the
249 economic value achieved by selection on P_0 .

250 In this example, production performance refers to nursery stage growth rate of pigs in a disease
251 challenge test. The same calculations could be applied to other relevant production traits of the

252 grower-finisher pig such as post-nursery growth rate, feed intake or mortality, as well as to
253 reproductive performance of sows, preferably recorded in field conditions. Given the devastating
254 effects of PRRS on reproduction traits (30), the associated economic value for resilience as
255 measured in terms of reproductive performance may well be higher than that presented in the
256 example above.

257 **4. Obstacles for genetic improvement of disease resilience in practice**

258 The above reaction norm model has proven useful for modelling the interaction between resilience
259 component traits, and for deriving economic values that can serve as the basis for cost-benefit
260 analyses.

261 In this Section 4 we address several hurdles that may hinder the application of such models for
262 actual data analysis and for genetic improvement of disease resilience in practice. Section 5 then
263 proposes solutions.

264 **4.1. Resilience component traits are difficult to measure or estimate**

265 Reaction norm models with ambient temperature as the physically recorded independent variable
266 have been used frequently to study heat resilience in ruminants and pigs (31-36). Temperature
267 recordings are easily obtained from meteorology services or from in-house recording. By contrast,
268 the various parameters that feature in our Figure 1 (i.e. the within-host pathogen burden PB_w , the
269 environmental pathogen burden PB_E and the performance potential P_0) come with considerable
270 recording challenges. In addition to that, the reaction norm approach itself presents some challenges
271 of a statistical nature, in particular for estimating tolerance.

272 PB_w requires quantification of the amount of pathogen carried by a host animal, which involves
273 methods ranging from counting ectoparasites (e.g. (37) for millimeter-long copepods on a sedated
274 fish), microscope counting of endoparasite eggs in fecal samples (e.g. (38)), to running PCR DNA

275 or RNA assays to establish bacterial or viral load in blood or tissue samples (e.g. (39, 40)). All
276 these methods are well-established but require skilled operators and often specialized equipment,
277 and therefore carry significant cost. For example, Thorvaldsen et al. (41) mention 15-80 minutes
278 work for 3 people to count the copepods on 20 salmon (which would cost the farm at least € 1 to € 5
279 per animal; tinyurl.com/rs4tltk); outsourced fecal egg counting is charged at € 5 to € 15 per sample
280 in the UK, the Netherlands and Australia (tinyurl.com/wqs99tp, tinyurl.com/rzkronj,
281 tinyurl.com/w7n2tu3); a PCR assay of PRRS viremia is charged at € 27 to € 42 per sample in the
282 UK, Belgium and USA (tinyurl.com/wqs99tp, tinyurl.com/w4ct6ud, tinyurl.com/t5vsu9q,
283 tinyurl.com/r99p5lu). In comparison, outsourced performance testing of pigs for growth rate and
284 ultrasound body composition in USA is charged at € 3.5 per animal (tinyurl.com/v82tyqt). Hence
285 PB_w recording is not prohibitively difficult, but it is costly. A decade and a half ago, the same was
286 true for genomic prediction in livestock breeding – this is a matter of cost-benefit analysis.

287 Direct measures of PB_E, the within-host equivalent of the environmental exposure dose
288 corresponding to a reference host with zero resistance, rarely exist. In practice, PB_E may be
289 approximated by some percentile of the highest observed PB_w values in the population
290 experiencing the same infectious challenge, effectively shifting the reference from a host with zero
291 resistance to the least resistant hosts in the dataset. Similar to the common approach of using the
292 population mean performance as a proxy of environmental pathogen burden (42), this approach
293 relies on the assumption that the sampling distribution is a valid representation of the full PB_w
294 distribution in each environment.

295 In controlled challenge trials with a single specific pathogen, P₀ may be quantified as the observed
296 performance prior to infection or, on a genetic level, from the performance of genetically related
297 unchallenged control animals (e.g. (43)). Outside such trials, genetic estimates of P₀ may be derived
298 from performance measures of genetically related individuals in "clean" farming environments,

299 such as a nucleus farm in pig or poultry breeding. As these are unlikely to be entirely free of
300 pathogens, P_0 will mostly be underestimated to an unknown extent. Alternatively, a wide enough
301 spread of PB_w in the data (see the next paragraph) may allow for the intercept estimate as a robust
302 proxy for P_0 for each individual in the data.

303 Tolerance is a difficult trait to estimate as the slope of a reaction norm of performance on PB_w
304 because this requires multiple measures of the independent (PB_w) and dependent variable (P), either
305 within the individual (which would require longitudinal data over time, see Section 5.3) or, in the
306 context of animal breeding, across genetically related individuals such as within daughter groups of
307 AI sires. With regard to quantification, recall that the approximate standard error (se) of an
308 estimated linear regression coefficient \hat{b}_{yx} of y on x is $se(\hat{b}_{yx}) \approx \sqrt{\frac{\hat{\sigma}_y^2}{n \hat{\sigma}_x^2} - \frac{\hat{b}_{yx}^2}{n}}$. It follows that
309 reliable estimates of tolerance reaction norm slopes (particularly shallow ones with small b^2) would
310 require many observations (large n) with a large variation in the independent variable (here PB_w).
311 The data used in our case study of Section 3.2 form a good example of a dataset that is inadequate
312 in this respect and also suffers from a lack of recording performance at zero PB_w .

313 Given these financial, logistical and statistical hurdles, the question arises whether it is worth
314 collecting PB_w measures at all. Few routine breeding programmes to date include routine measures
315 of PB_w . A common approach of pig, poultry and fish breeding companies is to select for reduced
316 disease or mortality rates, or for high production performance based on data recorded on close
317 relatives of nucleus selection candidates, grown in commercial conditions with natural pathogen
318 burden (e.g. (44-46)). The latter approach is equivalent to black-box selection for improved
319 resilience with unknown PB_E and PB_w . Mulder and Rashidi (12) performed simulations to compare
320 such an approach to explicit selection for the component traits *with* PB_w records, essentially
321 considering selection on an EBV for resilience as index selection for resistance and tolerance. They

322 concluded that such black-box selection for resilience is "an effective way to increase tolerance and
323 resistance [...] provided that both are not strongly unfavorably correlated". Based on their Figure
324 4A, "strongly unfavorably correlated" starts at a genetic correlation of -0.4 : that is where the
325 product of the simulated ΔG values of their resistance and tolerance traits (i.e. the ΔG of resilience)
326 approaches zero or even changes sign to become unfavorable (note that their resistance and
327 tolerance traits are equivalent to PB_w and β of our Figure 1, and they calculate resilience as $\beta \times$
328 PB_w , so that the signs are opposite to what we show here). In other words: as always when selecting
329 on a composite trait as such, responses of the component traits are uncertain and depend on the
330 genetic architecture around them: "the genetic correlation [...] has a high impact on the selection
331 responses in resistance and tolerance, and selection on resilience may lead to an unfavorable
332 response in resistance or tolerance" (12). Some practical consequences are considered in the next
333 section.

334 **4.2. Trade-offs between component traits**

335 Antagonistic genetic correlations among selection traits may represent trade-offs between various
336 biological functions; they form an important constraint in animal and plant evolution, and in
337 livestock and crop breeding ((2, 47, 48, chapter 30). The caveat of such trade-offs for disease
338 resilience was pointed out by Råberg et al. (49): "in the agricultural sector, attempts to select for
339 increased yield in the face of parasite challenge may come to nothing (or even make things worse)
340 if there is a trade-off between resistance and tolerance". Theoretical models predict that trade-offs
341 between tolerance and resistance exist if these are controlled by alternative immune pathways that
342 require energy resources (50-52). If these are limited (e.g. due to infection-induced anorexia or
343 poor energy intake or maintenance), preferential resource allocation towards one set of mechanisms
344 confers fitness costs to the other with resulting trade-offs.

Commenté [PK1]: Chapter 30 is of (48) only. Perhaps do (2; 47; 48, chapter 30). And we have two leading brackets here.

345 In livestock breeding, one-sided selection for increased production performance has been shown to
346 lead to compromised animal robustness due to trade-offs between performance and fitness functions
347 (53-55). The reaction norm model studies for heat resilience mentioned in Section 4.1 report nine
348 estimates of the genetic correlation between performance and heat resilience; one of these is
349 favourable ($r_G = +0.3$), the other eight are unfavourable and range from -0.4 to -0.8 .

350 For any serious animal breeding program, ignoring potential trade-offs between production and
351 fitness traits can have strongly damaging consequences in terms of societal acceptability and
352 commercial credibility (see (56, tinyurl.com/y9m8c8qe) and Rutherford et al. 2013, for a real-life
353 example on litter size versus preweaning mortality in pigs). Sustainable breeding seeks to avoid this
354 by including all the relevant component traits of a composite in the selection criterion. As outlined
355 above, this has not yet been achieved in the case of disease resilience.

356 The calculations of the economic value of PRRS resilience traits in the case-study of section 3.2
357 compare the responses of selecting for performance in an infection-free environment (P_0) to
358 selecting on R and T in an infectious environment, assuming that all these traits are genetically
359 independent, thus ignoring potential trade-offs. A more appropriate selection criterion would be an
360 index of P_0 , R and T to represent the breeding goal trait P_{PBE} , where the estimated breeding values
361 (EBVs) of P_0 , R and T are weighted by the MEVs as derived from equations (2b) and (3b). The
362 resulting genetic improvement in the traits is commonly predicted (to support cost-benefit analyses)
363 by selection index theory, which requires estimates for the genetic and phenotypic (co)variances of
364 the traits. Lough et al. (28) provide several of these, but could not estimate the covariance between
365 R and T. Some of the other parameters can be derived as described in the additional file, with as the
366 most striking result an approximation of the genetic correlation between P_0 and the tolerance slope
367 β of -0.99 . Although correlation estimates would need to be verified with better data, it is clear that

Commenté [AW2]: Did not have reference

Commenté [PK3R2]: Rutherford KMD, Baxter EM, Ask B, Berg P, D'Eath RB, Jarvis S, Jensen KK, Lawrence AB, Moustsen VA, Robson SK, Roehe R, Thorup F, Turner SP, Sandøe P. The ethical and welfare implications of large litter size in the domestic pig: challenges and solutions. *Animal Welfare* 2013; 22:199-218.

368 in such as strongly antagonistic system, it would be very difficult to generate ΔG for growth
369 potential and disease tolerance simultaneously.

370 Up to now in livestock breeding, much of the R&D focus around disease resilience has been on
371 resistance. Considering tolerance as an explicit selection trait is a relatively novel idea (see e.g. (10)
372 for reviews and recent exploratory examples, as well as (57) or (58). If the genetic correlation
373 between the traits is unfavorable, a breeding program that selects for improved host resistance faces
374 the risk of gradually decreasing host tolerance (and thus potentially also decreasing host resilience).
375 These consequences are further exacerbated if the pathogen co-evolves successfully to neutralize
376 host resistance (52). In this case a scenario with selection for increased resistance under
377 unfavourable genetic correlations will paradoxically lead to reduced tolerance, higher infection load
378 and neutralized resistance, and therefore to reduced resilience. And as far as those unfavourable
379 genetic correlations are actually unknown, this may easily lead any animal breeding program into
380 the societal acceptability and commercial credibility issues mentioned above – to be avoided
381 whenever possible.

382 Such avoidance would require reliable estimates of genetic correlations between disease resistance
383 and tolerance. But estimating genetic correlations is a notoriously demanding task in general (e.g.
384 (59) pp. 642-644), and the hard-to-measure character of tolerance (Section 4.1) only adds to this.

385 **Figure 2 to appear here.**

386 This is illustrated in Figure 2a, which depicts published resistance-tolerance correlation estimates
387 with their confidence intervals from various studies in animals and plants. The correlation estimates
388 span a wide range from -0.6 to $+0.5$, so in practice one may expect any value for the host and
389 pathogen population under study. Without actual data analysis, it is impossible to predict whether
390 trade-offs between resistance and tolerance exist. Furthermore, most of the confidence intervals

391 include a zero correlation, demonstrating the high uncertainty in quantifying this relationship even
392 when data are available.

393 Differences in the approaches to quantify resistance and tolerance, with PB_w only included in some
394 of them, may account for some of the uncertainty in the correlation estimates and their observed
395 variation between the studies of Figure 2a. Results from more unified experimental approaches are
396 depicted in Figure 2b, which illustrates the relationship between resistance and tolerance in various
397 inbred mouse strains against (i) malaria, (ii) a nematode or (iii) a bacterium, where resistance was
398 estimated as the inverse of PB_w and tolerance as the regression of a performance trait on PB_w as
399 outlined in our Section 2. Similar to the correlation estimates for outbred livestock (Figure 2a), the
400 relationship between resistance and tolerance varies considerably between different types of host
401 and pathogen strains.

402 In summary of Section 4: evidence suggests that the genetic correlation between resistance and
403 tolerance can be very favourable or very unfavourable or anything in between, and will be very
404 expensive to quantify; not only because genetic correlation estimates are data-hungry in general, but
405 also because this system requires recording of PB which is expensive in its own right. The reaction
406 norm model constitutes a conceptually attractive and analytically elegant but expensive model for
407 routine resilience breeding value estimation. Section 5 discusses potential routes forward.

408 **5. The future: Four alternative approaches**

409 **5.1. The purist approach**

410 The "purist" approach for the setup of a disease resilience breeding program would be to start with
411 PB (and production) recording until the data volume is sufficient for estimating the genetic
412 correlation between resistance and tolerance, and estimate the genetic parameters and evaluate the
413 possibly antagonistic system. If trade-offs exist, continued routine recording of PB would be

414 required for decomposing resilience into its component traits to be implemented into a selection
415 index that effectively balances the trade-offs. But when there is no evidence for such trade-offs,
416 decomposing resilience is no longer necessary and reaction-norms can be calculated based on
417 cheaper proxies for the environmental pathogen burden, such as the mean production performance
418 of each individual's contemporary group (like Mulder and Rashidi's (12) simulated scenario without
419 PB recording in our Section 4.1). This approach is commonly used to model general resilience to a
420 nondescript mixture of infectious and non-infectious stressors (e.g. (42)). Real-life studies using
421 such a model were summarized by Knap and Su (60, their Table 3), who also showed that the
422 statistical method of Su et al. (61) to estimate all the parameters of the reaction norm system (i.e. P_0 ,
423 β , and the value of the independent variable) in a single-step analysis produces more robust
424 statistics than the conventional contemporary group approach. This method requires production
425 records only, but poses strong demands on their volume and genetic structure; making use of a
426 genomic relationship matrix in its mixed model equations can be expected to increase the accuracies
427 of all the estimates including those of the independent variable.

428 One of the major obstacles of this purist approach to a resilience breeding programme that
429 appropriately handles trade-offs is the necessity to measure PB, at least initially. For systems for
430 which this is unfeasible, various approaches have been proposed involving proxy traits, such as
431 immune parameters or routinely collected health records, to quantify host resistance or the infection
432 challenge prevalent in a specific environment (e.g. (62-66)). These would need to be carefully
433 evaluated before implementing them into breeding programmes, and thus require significant
434 investment in time and money. With the advent of high-throughput genomics and high-resolution
435 automated phenotyping technologies, alternative solutions to breeding disease resilient livestock
436 that do not use classical reaction norms are now emerging. These alternatives are considered in the
437 next sections.

438 **5.2. Targeting QTL beneficial for both resistance and tolerance**

439 Evidence from a plethora of genome-wide association studies in livestock suggests that disease
440 resistance, tolerance and resilience are mostly under polygenic control, with a handful of genes of
441 relatively large effect (e.g. (5, 17, 67-69)). This implies that ΔG in the resilience traits will be
442 necessarily gradual and may require many generations of selection to achieve complete resistance
443 or tolerance, if at all possible. One possible approach to minimize the risk of undesirable outcomes
444 of selection due to hidden trade-offs may be to focus on overlapping genomic loci with identified
445 large positive effects on both traits (e.g. (70)). Alternatively, recalling the challenges of estimating
446 genetic parameters for tolerance reaction norms, one could focus on candidate loci with known
447 large effect on disease resistance, and subsequently determine their specific effect on tolerance.
448 This has been exemplified for PRRS, where GWAS studies identified a site on pig chromosome
449 SSC4 where a major QTL explained 10 to 20 % of the total genetic variance in resistance and
450 resilience to PRRS (71). Subsequent studies found that this QTL is also significantly associated
451 with tolerance to PRRS, with the genetically more resistant pigs being also more tolerant (28).
452 Consideration of such QTL with known beneficial pleiotropic effects on both traits may be a
453 promising short term strategy to gradually improve resistance and tolerance simultaneously in the
454 absence of reliable genetic correlation estimates.

455 **5.3. Targeting complete resistance or complete tolerance**

456 One way to avoid undesirable scenarios of unknown genetic correlations (Section 4.2) would be to
457 increase resistance or tolerance (both continuous traits, as per above) not gradually but completely,
458 preferably in a few rapid modification steps. Equations (1a) and (1b) and Figure 1 illustrate that
459 completely resistant animals do not need any tolerance to achieve high performance levels under
460 infectious challenge; and likewise, for completely tolerant animals the pathogen burden level is
461 irrelevant.

462 Such rapid modification steps would require a host-pathogen mechanism with a high host
463 heritability and a high prediction accuracy for the trait under consideration, so that selection would
464 achieve results quickly. In practice, this is most easily achieved if the trait has a simple genetic
465 architecture, i.e. is to a large extent controlled by a single gene. We give here three examples where
466 such rapid improvements were achieved through selection on a single DNA marker, in two cases
467 without significant knowledge of the underlying biological mechanisms.

468 First, marker-assisted selection for resistance to transmissible spongiform encephalopathy (scrapie)
469 in sheep, based on selection for particular genotypes of the *PNRP* gene which modulates much of
470 the variation in susceptibility to developing scrapie. In the UK, an increase of the favorable allele
471 frequency in young rams from 50 % to 69 % (Dawson et al. 2008, Table II) reduced the observed
472 national scrapie prevalence to close to zero in nine years i.e. three to four sheep generations
473 (Boelaert et al. 2016, his Table 14). In the Netherlands, a similar allele frequency increase in the
474 ewe population from 38 % to 65 % caused a similar prevalence reduction in seven years i.e. three
475 sheep generations (Hagenaars et al. 2018, their Figure 5).

476 Second, marker-assisted selection in pigs for resistance against *Escherichia coli* caused by a lack of
477 the cell receptors for the attachment of the bacterial adhesins (72). *E. coli* F4 resistance in the sow
478 populations of two Danish breeds increased from 0 to 80 %, and from 5 to 100 %, in six years i.e.
479 four pig generations ((3), his Figure 11). *E. coli* F18 resistance in the AI boar populations of two
480 Swiss breeds increased from 39 to 100 % in four years, and from 30 to 100 % in seven years, i.e. in
481 three to five pig generations (73).

482 Third, marker-assisted selection for reduced mortality due to infectious pancreatic necrosis (IPN) in
483 Atlantic salmon, based on a DNA marker developed by Moen et al. (74) and Houston et al. (75),
484 which explains ~98% of the genetic variation in mortality. Selection for this gene reduced the
485 annual number of IPN outbreaks in Norwegian farms from 223 to 23 in nine years i.e. three salmon

Commenté [AW4]: Could not find

Commenté [PK5R4]: Dawson M, Moore R, Bishop S. Progress and limits of PrP gene selection policy. *Veterinary Research, BioMed Central*. 2008; 39 (4):1-12. doi: 10.1051/vetres:2007064.hal-00902922

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Commenté [PK7R6]: Boelaert F, Hugas M, Pelaez AO, Rizzi V, Stella P, Van Der Stede Y. The European Union summary report on data of the surveillance of ruminants for the presence of transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (TSEs) in 2015. *EFSA Journal* 2016; 14(12):4643. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2016.4643

Commenté [AW8]: Could not find

Commenté [PK9R8]: Hagenaars TJ, Melchior MB, Windig JJ, Bossers A, Davidse A, van Zijderveld FG. Modelling of strategies for genetic control of scrapie in sheep: The importance of population structure. *PLoS ONE*. 2018; 13(3): e0195009. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0195009>

486 generations (76, tinyurl.com/y9gq3wyc). In light of the trade-off concerns raised in Section 4, the
487 outcome of this black-box selection for resilience is remarkable given that the impact of the
488 underlying gene on resistance and tolerance was unknown. Only later studies revealed that the
489 favourable allele for reduced IPN mortality conferred increased resistance to infection as well as to
490 infection transmission (thus effectively reducing PB_E in the population) without significantly
491 impacting the mortality rate of infected individuals, i.e. their tolerance to infection (77). In other
492 words, the observed increase in resilience was due to a fortunate combination of favourable or
493 neutral gene effects on the various resilience components simultaneously. There are currently too
494 few real-world examples of marker-assisted selection for improved disease resistance or resilience
495 to determine whether this combination is the norm or the exception. However, the examples shown
496 in Figure 2 would suggest that such fortune should not be taken for granted.

497 The alternative route to achieve complete resistance (or tolerance) would be to move away from the
498 classical gradual selection approaches, and exploit (i) detailed biological knowledge of the relevant
499 resilience mechanism and (ii) novel genomic technology to manipulate it. Genome editing is a
500 promisingly powerful methodology here, and we may expect much development in this field just
501 like in plant breeding (e.g.(78) for resistance against mildew in wheat). Ruan et al. (79) and
502 Proudfoot & Burkard (80) describe the current state of the art in animal breeding. PRRS resistance
503 in pigs constitutes one of the most promising examples, where a disruption of the CD163 gene
504 (either through knock-out of the complete gene or a simple deletion of its exon 7) makes pigs
505 completely resistant to infection with the PRRS virus, in the latter case without loss of the original
506 physiological functionality of the protein (81-84).

507 The important point here is that this approach could not have been developed based on scanning
508 procedures like GWAS that rely on natural polymorphisms to detect useful information. The CD163
509 gene was identified through earlier in-vitro studies to code for the host protein domain that is

510 hijacked by the virus to enable the release of its genome into the host macrophage (85). However,
511 extensive GWAS and CD163-focused sequencing studies worldwide have detected no natural
512 polymorphism at the relevant locus (86, 87) or produced signals in very different parts of the gene
513 (88, 89).

514 In summary, achieving complete genetic resistance or tolerance to infection requires identification
515 of genes with a very large effect on these traits. The few existing examples in livestock suggest that
516 such genes are rare or difficult to identify without detailed biological knowledge of the relevant
517 resilience mechanisms. Novel genomic tools may accelerate the discovery of such genes. The main
518 logistical challenge will be to rapidly disseminate the beneficial alleles into the production pyramid,
519 before the pathogen evolves to neutralize the desired gene function.

520 **5.4. Moving towards dynamic resilience indicators**

521 A fourth alternative for genetic improvement of disease resilience is to completely step away from
522 the reaction norm approach to quantify resilience, and consider fundamentally different approaches
523 emerging from resilience studies in other fields of research. Such alternative approaches, with
524 origins in mathematical dynamical systems theory, have recently been put forward for livestock
525 breeding, where resilience is defined as "the capacity of the animal to be minimally affected by a
526 disturbance or to rapidly return to the state pertained before exposure to a disturbance" (25, 90, 91).
527 Resilience in this context thus characterizes how an animal responds, over time, to a single
528 disturbance such as an infection.

529 To estimate the capacity of an animal to resist or to rapidly recover from the perturbation caused by
530 this disturbance, longitudinal measures of performance and possibly also health before, during, and
531 ideally after the perturbation period are required. Such time-series data of relevant response
532 variables are increasingly becoming routinely available in livestock systems through the rapid rise

533 in technologies for automated data recording of traits such as milk yield, body weight and feed
534 intake, as well as indicators of infection severity, immune responsiveness or health such as somatic
535 cell counts or infrared measures of body temperature. This offers opportunities to explore new
536 analytical tools to generate dynamic resilience indicators (92). Below we discuss some recent
537 advances relevant to livestock breeding.

538 **5.4.1. 2D resilience trajectories**

539 We come back to the PRRS data introduced at the end of Section 3, to illustrate how individual time
540 series data of PB_w and performance can give rise to informative 2D resilience trajectories. In
541 Section 3 a pig's static resilience to PRRS was described by its average growth rate over a fixed
542 infection period, where static resistance was quantified by the area under the viremia curve over that
543 period, and (static) tolerance was estimated as the slope of the reaction norm of growth rate against
544 $AUC(\log VL)$.

545 **Figure 3 to appear here.**

546 Figure 3 shows data on two animals from that same challenge experiment: the courses of PB_w and
547 growth rate over time and, more informatively, the associated reaction norms and the dynamic
548 trajectories of growth rate versus PB_w . Both reaction norms have slope estimates with high standard
549 errors, so that neither of them differs significantly from zero or from the other one ($P > 0.67$). The
550 dynamic resilience trajectories in Figure 3b are constructed using the same traits (growth rate and
551 PB_w) as the static resilience measures, but harness the coupled time trends in these traits. This way,
552 the trajectories not only illustrate the extent to which the animal is affected in terms of infection
553 severity and performance, but also the route to recovery to its pre-infection performance state
554 corresponding to zero PB_w . In this example, both animals show similar viremia trends (i.e. similar
555 resistance), but the black one does not grow over the whole 7-week infection period, whereas the

556 white one experiences a temporary reduction in growth associated with the initial decline in
557 viremia, followed by a steady increase in growth as PB_w reduces to zero. Overall, the black animal
558 is less resilient to the infection than the white one, although the slope estimates suggest the
559 opposite.

560 These dynamic trajectories have the advantage over reaction norms that they capture how resistance
561 and tolerance mechanisms interact over time, without the need to disentangle and explicitly estimate
562 these traits (93, 94). More generally, such 2D resilience trajectories, which can also be constructed
563 using different resistance or performance indicators (e.g. immune response measures (95)), provide
564 additional information on animal's responses that cannot be captured by reaction norms. For
565 example, they reveal which stages of infection are associated with the strongest loss of
566 performance, which may provide useful insight into underlying resilience mechanisms and target
567 genes or for devising effective timely and targeted treatment (96). Implementation of such
568 trajectories into practical breeding programmes will require novel analytical approaches to derive
569 meaningful and reliable indicators that capture the trajectory characteristics and that lend
570 themselves to routine genetic evaluation. Methods for analyzing such complex trajectories, whose
571 patterns cannot be described by mathematical functions, have just started to emerge (94, 95, 97-99),
572 and as such the value to animal breeding is yet to be determined.

573 **5.4.2. Black-box 1D dynamic resilience indicators**

574 When longitudinal measures of PB_w or other immune parameters are not available for constructing
575 2D resilience trajectories, dynamic resilience indicators of individual animals can be constructed
576 from temporal profiles of production measures alone, such as the growth rate profile in Figure 3a.
577 This has been exemplified in recent studies that derived such indicators from temporary reductions
578 or day-to-day variations in milk yield or body weight (100, 101), or from daily feed intake data (25,

579 90, 102). Although these studies differ in their exact approaches to derive dynamic resilience
580 indicators, the common underlying assumption is that the (known or unknown) stressor causes
581 temporal deviations in the performance traits, and that resilience can be quantified by the scale,
582 pattern or duration of these deviations: more resilient animals experience less pronounced
583 deviations from their target performance trajectory (90, 92).

584 In contrast to the above described 2D resilience trajectories that describe how infection severity and
585 performance interact over time, the 1D dynamic resilience indicators that are based on deviations in
586 performance alone, need to be assessed with regards to their informative value for resilience (90).
587 For example, anorexia (a temporary reduction of food intake) forms an important coping
588 mechanism of infected animals (103); a large deviation in feed intake may therefore correspond to
589 high rather than low resilience. Putz et al. (102) found moderate to strong genetic correlations
590 between (i) disease resilience indicators based on daily variability in feed intake or feed intake
591 duration and (ii) mortality and treatment rate in a natural disease challenge environment comprising
592 a cocktail of pathogens. Similarly, Elgersma et al. (101) found that on a genetic level, cows with
593 low variance in milk yield deviations tended to have fewer production-related diseases and longer
594 longevity. By contrast, Berghof et al. (100) found close-to-zero genetic correlations between body
595 weight deviations and natural antibodies, questioning the validity of the former as disease resilience
596 indicators in their dataset.

597 **5.4.3. Pros and cons of dynamic resilience indicators**

598 Similar to reaction norms calculated with or without PB measures, 2D resilience trajectories
599 including measures of PB and performance are more informative for a specific disease than 1D
600 trajectories based on performance records alone. Capturing more information generally leads to
601 increased understanding of the biological system (e.g. the relationship between resistance and

602 tolerance) and hence also to greater chances of bringing it under control. These advantages need to
603 be weighted against the additional recording requirements in a cost-benefit analysis.

604 Black-box 1D dynamic resilience indicators may offer attractive resilience measures in situations
605 where the stressor or PB_w is unknown, or where multiple pathogens and other stressors are likely to
606 be present simultaneously, such as in a typical production farm (90, 91, 102). Hence they have been
607 coined as "general resilience" in contrast to resilience to a specific disease. However, this
608 terminology may be somewhat misleading as it still applies to one particular environment only. It is
609 not known whether an animal with high resilience in one environment would also have high
610 resilience in a different environment where different combinations of pathogens are circulating. It is
611 unlikely that similar resilience responses will occur across environments with different pathogen
612 burden. This implies that across farms (or over time) the variable PB_E levels (or relevant proxies as
613 described above) will still have to be quantified. Longitudinal performance records on individuals
614 or (more realistically) groups of relatives in a range of environments could then produce resilience
615 estimates both within and across environments, using the dynamic resilience indicators within each
616 environment as the response variable of the across-environmental reaction norm model. In other
617 words, dynamic resilience indicators complement but do not replace the reaction norm model; the
618 latter remains the only method to accurately estimate resilience across environments.

619 **6. Final remarks**

620 All of the above has focused on the resilience of individual animals. At a higher integration level,
621 *herd resilience* depends on "the adaptive capacity of the animals in the herd, together with the
622 management decisions that affect the performance trajectories and local environment of the
623 animals" (104). In terms of disease resilience, a crucial component of this "local environment of the
624 animals" is the environmental pathogen burden, and a large part of it will often be influenced by

625 pathogen transmission among animals in the herd. This introduces the animal-intrinsic trait *host*
626 *infectivity*, i.e. the propensity of an animal, once infected, to transmit infection to others (105). Host
627 infectivity, resistance and tolerance are likely interdependent, as the capacity of an animal to infect
628 its groupmates logically depends on its own resistance and tolerance to the pathogen. In particular,
629 tolerant animals that do not eradicate the pathogen from their system via resistance, may continue
630 shedding it into their micro-environment (106-108). Individual resilience, when dominated by
631 tolerance, may thus be counterproductive to herd resilience. It follows that a complete quantitative
632 treatment of the topic of disease resilience should include the trait *host infectivity* in addition to
633 resistance and tolerance; see e.g. (77, 106), and (109) for approaches to calculate the economic
634 value of selective breeding for reduced disease transmission. However, this is beyond the scope of
635 this paper.

636 **Conclusions**

637 Reaction norm models have proven useful for quantifying the relative effects on disease resilience
638 of environmental pathogen burden and of the animal's production potential, resistance and
639 tolerance, and for quantifying the so far unknown economic values. Their effective implementation
640 in livestock breeding programmes is currently hampered by the lack of adequate tools to measure or
641 accurately estimate these resilience component traits, in particular pathogen burden. Likely trade-
642 offs between resilience component traits, if not properly accounted for, can jeopardize genetic
643 improvement in disease resilience. Recent advances in affordable and accurate high-throughput
644 genomic and high-resolution automated phenotyping technologies, as well as in genome editing,
645 accompanied by promising developments in statistical methods adapted to these data, offer exciting
646 new opportunities to breed livestock with greater genetic resilience to current and future infectious
647 diseases.

648

649 **List of abbreviations**

650 *If abbreviations are used in the text they should be defined in the text at first use, and a list of*
651 *abbreviations can be provided.*

652 R Host Resistance

653 T Host Tolerance

654 P_0 Host performance potential (i.e. performance when pathogen burden is zero)

655 PB_E environmental pathogen burden

656 PB_W within-host pathogen burden

657 P_{PBE} realized performance at environmental pathogen burden PB_E

658 P_{PBW} realized performance at within-host pathogen burden PB_W

659 $\Delta R, \Delta T$ Change in host resistance and tolerance, respectively

660 ΔG Genetic gain

661 MEV Marginal economic value

662

663 **Declarations** *(please see our editorial policies for more information:*

664 <https://www.biomedcentral.com/getpublished/editorial-policies#ethics+and+consent>). *If any of the*
665 *sections are not relevant to your manuscript, please include the heading and write 'Not applicable'*
666 *for that section.*

667

668 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

669 Not applicable

670 **Consent for publication**

671 Not applicable

672

673 **Availability of data and materials**

674 This article only used data already published. We refer to the original articles for information on
675 data availability.

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682 **Authors' contributions**

683 Both authors contributed equally to the conceptualisation and writing of the manuscript. Both
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687 **Author's information** (optional)

688

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990 **Figures** (only titles and legends should be included in main text; for more information on

991 preparing figures, please see here [https://gsejournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-](https://gsejournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript#preparing+figures)
992 [guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript#preparing+figures](https://gsejournal.biomedcentral.com/submission-guidelines/preparing-your-manuscript#preparing+figures))

993 **Figure 1. Reaction norm models for disease resilience.**

994 (a, b, c): A model of realized performance in infectious conditions (P_{PBE}) in relation to
995 environmental pathogen burden (P_{BE}), host performance potential (P_0), host resistance (R) and host
996 tolerance ($T = -1 / \beta$; note that $\beta \leq 0$) for two host animals (1, 2). Resistance reduces P_{BE} to within-
997 host pathogen burden (P_{BW}) which leads to performance recapture along the host's reaction norm to
998 the P_{PBE} level. Tolerance and resistance are favourably correlated in (a) and unfavourably in (b) and
999 (c); P_{BE} is lower in (c) than in (a) and (b).

1000 (d): A model of improving resilience through increases in R and T while keeping P_0 unchanged, see
1001 Section 3.1. The starting position (blue dot) is based on initial resistance level R and initial
1002 tolerance level T, with pathogen burden P_{PBW1} and performance P_{PBW1} . From there, resistance is
1003 increased by ΔR and tolerance is increased from T by ΔT to T' (a move to a shallower reaction
1004 norm); this leads to a new position following the green arrow, with performance P_{PBW2} (red dot).

1005
1006

1007 **Figure 2. Published estimates for the relationship between resistance and tolerance in**
1008 **plants and animals.**

1009 (a) Genetic correlation estimates between resistance and tolerance in various plant and animal
1010 species (quantified in ways that do not necessarily correspond to our Section 2). The error bars
1011 represent the 95 % confidence interval (± 1.96 standard errors around the estimate, some of these
1012 were derived from the published P values). The x- and y-axes have the same dimension and scale
1013 in order to separate the datapoints in a helpful way. Black symbols: infectious diseases, white
1014 symbols: other stressors. Data from (110) (*Arabidopsis* vs insects), (111) (*Ipomoea* vs insects),
1015 (112) (*Brassica* vs frost), (113) (*Mimulus* vs mosaic virus), (43) (tiger shrimp vs Taura virus),
1016 (114) (chicken vs ascites), (115) (*Solanum* vs insects), (116) (*Arabidopsis* vs frost and heat),
1017 (117) (sheep vs nematode), (70) (turbot vs skin parasite). (b) Black and white ovals: tolerance of
1018 five inbred mouse strains to the malaria parasite *Plasmodium chabaudi* (regression of body
1019 weight [black] or erythrocyte density [white] on pathogen load) in relation to the reverse of
1020 pathogen burden (data from (18), their Figure 3; ~30 animals per subclass). Red and blue ovals:
1021 tolerance of three inbred mouse strains to the nematode *Heligmosomoides bakeri* (correlation of
1022 carcass weight with two counts of pathogen load) in relation to the reverse of pathogen burden
1023 (data from (118); their Table 3 and Figure 1; 10 animals per subclass). Orange ovals: tolerance of
1024 four inbred mouse strains to the bacterium *Listeria monocytogenes* (regression of scaled body
1025 weight on pathogen load) in relation to the reverse of pathogen burden (data from (94); their
1026 Figure 2; 10 animals per strain, with two strains further sub-divided into survivors and non-
1027 survivors). Each oval represents the 68 % confidence interval around the bivariate mean (± 1.0
1028 standard error around the mean).

1029

1030

1031 **Figure 3. Reaction norms and dynamic resilience trajectories constructed from**
 1032 **longitudinal measures of pathogen burden and performance.**

1033 (a) Temporal profiles for viremia (P_{BW}) and growth rate (P_{PBW}) of two pigs infected with the
 1034 PRRS virus. (b) The associated reaction norms and dynamic resilience trajectories. Data from
 1035 (28). Datapoints represent observations, the solid trendlines and arrows in (b) show time trends.
 1036 The dashed lines in (b) represent the linear regression through the data (i.e. the reaction norm)
 1037 with slope estimate β and its standard error.

1038 Tables

1039 **Table 1. Cost of disease combat versus value of genetic improvement in (re)production traits.**

1040

area	year	species	disease ^a	feature	currency	total cost (M / year)	herd size ^b (M head)	cost per head	ΔG per head	cost / ΔG
Netherlands	1997	pig	CSF	cost of outbreak control ^c	EUR	2,340 ^d	15	153		
Taiwan	1997	ungulates	FMD	direct cost + export losses ^c	USD	1,600 ^d	12	135		
UK	2001	ungulates	FMD	cost of outbreak control ^c	GBP	8,000 ^d	42 ^{be}	190		
South Korea	2010	ungulates	FMD	cost of outbreak control ^c	USD	1,856 ^f	16	115		
China	2019	pig	ASF	cost of outbreak control ^c	USD	25,500 ^g	236 ^g	108 ^g		
Australia	2006	sheep	parasites	production losses + control cost	AUD	649 ^h	105	6.2	0.81 ⁱ	7.6
Netherlands	2007	ruminants	Bluetongue	cost of outbreak control	EUR	170 ^j	5.2 ^{bk}	37.3	14 ^m	2.7
England	2010	cattle	BTB	routine control cost	GBP	109 ⁿ	5.5 ^e	19.9	3.8 ^{ko}	5.2
Canada	2010	pig	PRRS	production losses	CAD	130 ^p	21	6.1	1.2 ^q	5.8
USA	2013	pig	PRRS	production losses	USD	1,142 ^r	112	10.2	2.2 ^s	4.7
Europe ^t	2013	pig	PRRS	production losses	EUR	1,660 ^u	252	6.6	1.6 ^v	4.1

1041

1042 Legend and references to Table 1 are in Additional file 1.

1043

1044 Additional files

1045 **Additional file 1**

1046 Format: .docx → .pdf

1047 Title: Estimated cost of combating infectious livestock diseases on the national level.

1048 Description: Legend and references to Table 1 of the main text.

1049

1050 **Additional file 2**

1051 Format: .docx → .pdf

1052 Title: Derivation of correlation estimates for performance potential and tolerance for the PRRS case
1053 study of section 3.2.

1054 Description: Mathematical derivations and results table.

1055